

**WAYS TO ACHIEVE INNOVATIVE RESULTS IN OUR COUNTRY IN THE CONTEXT OF
THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY**

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Abstract. *In this article, about the acceleration of the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals by digital technologies, the integration of digital technologies into all areas of business, ways to use the great potential of digital technologies for development, the principles of the digital economy, the concept of the digital economy, economic growth as a stimulus for the development of an information society based on the knowledge of social networks. suggestions regarding the factor are given.*

Key words: *digital transformation, digital technology, digital skills, digitization, inclusion, competence, strategic resource, tangible and intangible economic activity, information explosion.*

Digital technology offers enormous opportunities to accelerate the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals, but it can also widen socio-economic gaps for those who lack connectivity, affordable devices or the skills to use digital services.⁹

Digital transformation is the process of integrating digital technologies into all areas of business, changing the implementation of economic and social activities. While it is important to recognize that digital technology can bring enormous opportunities, such as accelerating progress towards achieving the Sustainable Development Goals, it also creates socio-economic gaps for those who lack access to the Internet, affordable devices or the skills to use digital services. can expand. Vulnerable people and groups who lack digital skills may be more vulnerable to online risks such as fraud, data breaches, theft and cyberbullying.

"The future is digital and will define how we live, work and interact with each other. Whether technology becomes an empowering force for good or creates more division and exclusion depends on the choices we make now."

To harness the great potential of digital technologies for development and leave no one behind, we must be intentional about driving technology development and national digital transformation in a direction that is both inclusive and sustainable.¹⁰

⁹ <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/tsifrovaya-ekonomika-preimuschestva-ugrozy-i-factory-vliyaniya#:~:text=На%20развитие%20цифровой%20экономики%20оказывают,р азработку%20и%20внедрение%20цифровых%20технологий.>

In order to harness the great potential of digital technologies for development and leave no one behind, we must constantly strive to advance technology and guide the national digital transformation in a direction that is both inclusive and sustainable.

Digitization is an important basis not only for development, but also for overcoming crises. Countries that have invested in digital infrastructure in the past have proven to have better resilience to the crisis.

Digital technologies also provide powerful tools and innovative solutions to help solve environmental problems. They are also widely used to promote climate resilience and protect those most at risk from natural disasters. Increasing computing power and more sophisticated modeling enable disaster simulation and recovery planning in climate emergencies. The growing amount of information available is giving us a better understanding and overview of our planet's natural resources and how we can build more sustainable lives and livelihoods, especially for the most vulnerable.

Digital technologies are shaping many areas and sectors of life, benefiting more people and enabling the most vulnerable to earn, learn, stay connected, communicate and provide essential services like education and health better and more efficiently, gives the opportunity to get.

However, digital technologies are not inherently inclusive. We need to design them thoughtfully and use them that way. For this reason, UNDP supports countries that seek to accelerate digital transformation, covering the entire society.

Now, companies need to develop comprehensive competency development programs for the future, which will help employees develop skills to work in new environments.

Employers identify the following competencies that are most in demand: digital skills, creativity, thinking and problem solving, interpersonal skills, awareness and self-management, ability to learn and openness to new things.

Interactions with each other are now reflected in activities in remote settings, the use of flexibility at work, and the active use of services and digital tools. The powers of the future are formed through this focus. But these competencies are also important in today's reality. Digital skills refer to the use of skills and knowledge to remotely equip an employee's workplace, configure or install all services necessary for effective functioning.

Also, there was a need to establish communication with other remote employees (colleagues, as well as suppliers, consumers) and a separate working group in general. The ability to learn quickly and be open to everything is in demand.

The productivity of employees taking into account remote work determines how quickly they adapt to new conditions and how they build their work process "in a new way" to achieve a given efficiency vector. The employee's psychological balance can be achieved through self-management skills and awareness of what is happening.

¹⁰ <https://www.undp.org/blog/three-ways-digital-transformation-accelerates-sustainable-and-inclusive-development>

The proposed competencies are more stable and, unlike professional skills, they do not become obsolete. Modern technologies, which develop critical and creative thinking, find application in faster adaptation to rapidly changing conditions and new requirements. But the extent to which such powers are necessary and socially important depends on the employee participating in the work process.¹¹

Digital economy is defined as an economy that focuses on digital technologies, i.e. it is based on digital and computing technologies. It essentially covers all [business](#), [economic](#), social, [cultural](#) etc. activities that are supported by the web and other digital communication technologies.¹²

The term was first coined in a book "The Digital Economy: Promise and Peril in the Age of Networked Intelligence" by author Don Tapscott in 1995.

There are three main components of this economy, namely,

- e-business
- e-business [infrastructure](#)
- [e-commerce](#)¹³

Principles of digital economy:

Digitized information has become a strategic resource, and network technologies have become the main organizing principle of the entire economy and society. A new generation of digital technologies is now generating unprecedented amounts of data and providing the necessary tools to harness this asset. With all this, the concept of "information explosion" was born in 1975 as an avalanche-like increase in the mass of various information in modern society.

¹¹

<https://1economic.ru/lib/112993#:~:text=Работодатели%20выделяют%20следующие%20наиболее%20востребованные,и%20открытость%20новому%20%5B1%5D.>

¹² <https://www.toppr.com/guides/business-environment/emerging-trends-in-business/digital-economy/>

¹³ <https://www.toppr.com/guides/business-environment/emerging-trends-in-business/digital-economy/>

The digital economy follows the principles of increasing profitability along with the continuous growth of tangible and intangible economic activities.

New business models are emerging to take advantage of bilateral markets. A two-way market is a meeting place between two agents interacting through an intermediary or platform. The involvement of both parties is fundamental to the development and success of each platform and to our understanding of the pricing strategies employed by market participants. In the context of the digital economy, two-way markets refer to online platforms. The new model of industrial production ("Industry 410") includes short production cycles for mass products, the global fragmentation of value chains, the creation of networks of production possibilities and the blurring of boundaries between producers, sellers and consumers based on decentralization. Profit maximization is a characteristic of the digital economy due to the positive influence of the network platform, and the value of a digital product or service increases with the size of the network without increasing costs.

One effect of the principle of increasing returns is that the costs of production and distribution have little or no relation to the volumes produced, but they must be paid for the initial investment.

The marginal cost of production is correspondingly close to zero, and therefore the digital economy is intensive in terms of intensity, digital products can be reproduced in very large quantities. Investments in platforms are initially high, but then decline as innovation becomes widespread among users. Thus, the return on investment increases.

The market in the digital economy follows a monopolistic or oligopolistic competition model and is often limited to a few large companies emerging through mergers and acquisitions.

Online platforms have encouraged the formation and development of new business models - two-way markets. Binary markets can be found in many industries, mainly in service offerings. Bilateral markets differ from offers in classical markets in their fundamental development.

The platform bears the cost of serving both groups and can collect revenue from each group. The two groups interact with each other and form a network with all the features. In a two-way market with network effects, the value of the platform for any given user depends largely on the number of users in the network. The price of the platform is increasing due to increasing demand from both sides.

The theory of markets is based on the idea of products and services serving two different groups of users, both sides of the market at the same time, through a platform that can be accessed via a computer, smartphone or tablet. One side of the market consists of positive network externalities from consumers using free or free access and services provided to consumers.

Two-way marketplaces are becoming more attractive as the number of users increases, they provide platforms with socio-demographic information, preferences, locations and consumption behavior on the platform.

The other side of the market includes the economic players involved in providing the platform. They benefit from positive network externalities proportional to the number of consumers. On one side of the market, the service price for agents is related to the number and quality of principals on the other. Platforms are funded by commissions or advertising from transactions between the two sides of the market. The business model of an online platform can also be implemented as a non-profit project - a crowdfunding platform or a subcultural community based on the donations of participants.

In conclusion, it can be said that the concept of digital economy can be seen as a stimulating factor of the development of the information society based on the knowledge of social networks, economic growth. Digitized information can represent an economic value and potential that is increasing day by day in strategic importance. The development of the digital economy is changing the way we think about economic development and the future of work. Bilateral markets using online platforms are increasingly gaining trust among entrepreneurs and corporations as an optimal business model.¹⁴

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¹⁴ <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/osnovnye-printsipy-kontseptsii-tsifrovoy-ekonomiki#:~:text=Цифровая%20экономика%20имеет%20четыре%20специфические,эффектов%20и%20использование%20больших%20данных.>